

PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITH THE ELEMENTS OF FLORA

Atkamova S.A.

Doctor of Scientific advisor: philosophy on philological science (PhD)

Haknazarova Mohinur Shomurodovna

Uzbek State World Languages University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7981636>

Abstract: The purpose of this article is to identify the structural and semantic features of phraseological units with the floristic component of the English. The novelty of the study lies in the fact that the authors carried out work on the systematization of phraseological units with phytonyms, namely the designations of fruits, in English language. The semantic analysis of phraseological units showed, on the one hand, similarity, and on the other hand, differences in the use of phytonyms as part of phraseological units close in meaning in the language.

Key words: phytonyms, semantic classification, apple, banana, cherry, connotive senses.

Flora represents all vegetation on the planet. The theory says that each type of plant that grows on its territory under certain conditions belongs to the flora of the region. The flora does not include the class of greenhouse, indoor plants. Phraseological units with a floristic component constitute a considerable part of the vocabulary and are of high usage.

In addition, the semantics of this group of phraseological units has cultural specificity, which should be taken into account in the translation process. Flora is the aggregate word given to plant life that exists or formerly grew in a certain location or across time. This generally refers to local plant life, but it may also relate to newly imported species. Latin names have been given to the Earth's vegetation. Flora was the goddess of flowers and plants in Greek mythology. She was the goddess of fertility in Roman mythology. Flora acquired the name for the Kingdom of Plants. Many plants have been symbols of England since the reign English Queen Victoria. These symbols allow you to explore features of the culture of the people, its values, traditions, realities. The symbol is a sign of reality, bearing in addition to subject-figurative meaning is another, culturally more valuable content. Plants can embody mythological ideas about the environment world, concretize them, which allows us to consider them archetypal symbols [Yakovleva 1994: 370].

There are two groups of estimated potential of phytonyms.

1. The evaluation component may be driven by objective properties of the plant: features of appearance, usefulness for practical activities, edibility or inedibility etc.

2. The evaluation component can be conditioned cultural characteristics of plants – religiously – mythological origin of plant names, resemblance to household items or parts of the body (human, animal, etc.)

Here the similarity is that the plant spreads its stems over earth, as if the hand of a blind man is groping for something to receive information; lion's mouth, lit. "lion's mouth" - "snapdragon". Here the similarity is that the opened flowers resemble the open mouth of a lion, therefore, in Russian it is also associated with the mouth of a lion. [Komarova 2006: 70–75].

Apple

The most active phraseologically phytonym, denoting fruit, in English is "apple". 1.The usually round, red or yellow, edible fruit of a small tree, *Malussylvestris*, of the rose family.2.The tree, cultivated in most temperate regions.3.The fruit of any of certain other species of tree of the same genus [Hornby 2010: 1654].

So, for example, a wormy or rotten apple in English used to mean externally attractive, but morally a spoiled person: the rotten apple "black sheep"; a bad apple a person in a group of good people" [Spears 1998: 97–99].

Phraseologisms - apple of discord - apple of discord, the apple of one's eye - the apple of the eye, the apple of Sodom - cute, but rotten, having their own the source of the Biblical story - actualize the associative seme.

In the English mentality, the phytonym "apple" conveys a deceptive success - Adam's apple - Adam's apple, due to reflection in English phraseology of the Biblical giving that near Sodom, located near the Dead Sea, beautiful apples grew, turned into smoke and ashes at the first touch.

Banana

From Oxford Dictionary: 1. Any of several treelike plants of the genus *Musa*, especially *M. acuminata*, having a terminal crown of large, entire leaves and a hanging cluster of fruits;.2. The elongated, edible fruit of these plants, having a thick yellowish to reddish skin and whitish, pulpy flesh [Hornby 2010: 458].

The image and symbol of this phytonym is reflected in phraseology:

to do / lose one's banana - lose control of yourself, go crazy

to drive one bananas - drive (smb.) crazy [Collins 1999: 60]

To sum up, the English language with its huge number of phraseological units is one of the richest in the world. All the events taking place in the UK are reflected in them: politics, sports, culture, everyday life (flora, fauna). Many become obsolete, but new ones come to replace them. Therefore, it is safe to say that the phraseological system of the English language will develop and multiply every day.

References:

1. Ayupova R. A., Sakhibullina K. A. Evaluative component of the meaning of phraseological and paremiological units with an ornithonym component (on the material of English, and Russian languages) // Philological Sciences. Questions of theory and practice. 2014. No. 4 (34). Part 3. C. 28-31
2. Kunin A. V. English-Russian phraseological dictionary / lit. ed. M. D. Litvinova. 4th edition, revised. and additional M.: Russian language, 1984. 944 p.
3. Litvinov P. P. 3500 English phraseological units and set phrases. Moscow: Astrel; AST, 2007. 288 p.
4. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/semanticheskie-osobennosti-frazeologicheskikh-edinit-s-komponentom-ornitonimom-v-angliyskom-nemetskom-i-russkom-yazykah>

